

NFDI4Energy Conference

2. NFDI4Energy Conference

10.5281/zenodo.15064826

© Authors. This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Published: 2025-03-21

Extending a Data-Centric Distributed Simulation Framework for the Energy Domain

Corinna Seiwert¹[\[https://orcid.org/0009-0004-0779-3186\]](https://orcid.org/0009-0004-0779-3186),
Nurbek Halikulov¹[\[https://orcid.org/0009-0003-1310-9734\]](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-1310-9734), and
Reinhard German¹[\[https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9071-4802\]](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9071-4802)

¹Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany

Abstract: The Data-centric Distributed Simulation (DaceDS) framework was developed to enable loose coupling of simulators from the traffic domain. In this work, we present a new concept for extending the framework to support more simulators and integrate new features towards a Simulation-as-a-Service for the NFDI4Energy platform.

Keywords: Data-Centric Distributed Simulation, Energy System Modeling, Simulation-as-a-Service

1 Introduction

The efficient use and continuous advancement of digital tools are crucial for addressing the challenges of the energy transition. In this context, the NFDI4Energy platform aims to provide flexible and interactive simulation solutions tailored to energy research needs. By integrating a Simulation-as-a-Service (SimaaS) approach, the platform simplifies the execution of co-simulations, enabling researchers to couple diverse models and simulators seamlessly [1]. SimaaS facilitates the integration of heterogeneous simulation tools, fosters interdisciplinary collaboration, and supports the realistic modeling of complex energy systems [2]. This scalable and user-friendly environment empowers researchers to execute and analyze complex simulation scenarios, driving innovative solutions for the energy transition.

To enhance the NFDI4Energy platform, we will extend the data-centric distributed simulation framework (DaceDS) [3], designed initially to couple simulators in the traffic domain. Our goal is to adapt DaceDS to meet the specific requirements of energy system research. This extension will enable the seamless coupling of various energy domain simulators and integrate data and models within a federated environment, facilitating the exploration of new research questions. Additionally, we will ensure that DaceDS can be effectively and efficiently integrated into the SimaaS offering of the NFDI4Energy platform.

2 Data-centric Architectural Concept

DaceDS is based on a data-centric architectural concept which, as shown in Figure 1, is divided into three layers. Each layer takes on a different task:

- Infrastructure/Core layer: The bottom layer defines how data is exchanged and stored between the components. DaceDS uses a middleware-based approach with the topic-based publish/subscribe messaging system Kafka for communication. The exchanged data is stored in a central data memory that all simulation components can access.
- Coupling layer: This layer specifies the simulator coupling mechanisms. Coupling is achieved by exchanging predefined data tuples based on a structured and rule-based procedure that enables flexible and consistent interaction between the various simulation components.
- Service/Application layer: This layer provides tools for managing domain and layer definitions and organizing the components and resources used.

The three-layer architecture of DaceDS ensures data consistency and flexibility when integrating simulators while allowing intuitive management and extension of the system [3].

Figure 1. Data-centric Architectural Concept of DaceDS [3]

3 Planned Extensions

In order to meet the specific requirements of the energy domain and to enable integration into the SimaaS of the NFDI4Energy platform, we are expanding the DaceDS framework in several areas:

- Integration of containers for efficient and scalable simulations.
- Extension of the coupling layer through the use of ontologies.
- Improvement of the Service/Application Layer with new features for scenario creation.
- Integration of additional simulators from the energy domain.

We have summarized these adjustments in figure 2. In SimaaS environments, developers rely on containers because they offer a lightweight virtualization technology. Containers bundle applications and their dependencies into a single image, allowing multiple simulation instances to run in parallel [1], which improves both the efficiency and the speed of getting results [4]. We, therefore, plan to implement containers in DaceDS to simplify integration into the SimaaS.

The energy domain is characterized by a high heterogeneity of the simulators used, making interoperability difficult. DaceDS uses domain and layer taxonomies to facilitate this interoperability. The domain taxonomy formally describes the concepts of

Figure 2. Extended Architectural Concept of DaceDS

a domain, such as the energy domain. The layer taxonomy organizes the concepts within a domain at different abstraction levels, usually represented by different simulators. We enrich the taxonomies with metadata and link them to ontology terms to further standardize them. In this way, we create a more consistent and universally valid description.

We integrate the following ontologies into DaceDS:

- Open Energy Ontology [5] for the energy domain.
- Common Core Ontologies [6] for generic concepts.
- SAREF4auto [7] for the transportation domain.
- The International Data Spaces Information Model [8] for the communication domain.

By integrating these ontologies, we reduce the redundancy in the taxonomies and considerably simplify the translation between layers.

Creating and configuring simulation scenarios remains a complex task, especially when coupling multiple simulators. We are integrating additional tools for model-based scenario creation to support researchers better in this process. Schwarz et al. [9] present an approach for an assisted creation process of co-simulation scenarios by using a catalog of simulation models and metadata descriptions of the content to assist the user during the modeling process. The description of simulation components and domains using ontologies also offers great potential for using large language models (LLMs). This technology can be used to automate tasks such as creating configuration files or models. Initial approaches by Dengler et al. [10] show how LLMs can generate Python scripts that function as inputs to a simulation environment.

Finally, we extend DaceDS with wrappers for specific simulators from the energy domain. These include:

- PyPSA [11]
- pandapower [12]
- OpenDSS [13]
- Simulators with cybersecurity analysis capabilities.

These planned enhancements aim to improve the functionality and usability of DaceDS and establish it as a component for the energy domain within NFDI4Energy.

4 Conclusion

The planned extensions to the DaceDS framework represent an important step towards meeting the specific requirements of the energy domain and enabling seamless integration into the NFDI4Energy platform's SimaaS. By integrating containers, we create an efficient and scalable infrastructure for simulations. Using ontologies to enrich the domain and layer taxonomies increases interoperability and facilitates the standardization of concepts and data. In addition, we improve usability through new scenario-creation features that utilize ontologies and support from LLMs. By integrating specific simulators from the energy domain, such as PyPSA or pandapower, we are expanding the range of applications of DaceDS and addressing key requirements in research and practice.

The planned extensions offer potential for improving research processes and provide a valuable basis for integrating feedback from the community and further developing the framework's functionalities in a targeted manner.

Data availability statement

Not applicable.

Underlying and related material

Not applicable.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: C.S.; Data curation: C.S.; Investigation: C.S., N.H.; Methodology: C.S.; Project administration: C.S.; Supervision: R.G.; Validation: C.S.; Visualization: C.S.; Writing – original draft: C.S.; Writing – review & editing: C.S., N.H., R.G.;

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

The authors would like to thank the German Federal Government, the German State Governments, and the Joint Science Conference (GWK) for their funding and support as part of the NFDI4Energy consortium. Funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – 501865131.

References

- [1] M. Gütlein and A. Djanatliev, "Modeling and simulation as a service using apache kafka," Jan. 2020, pp. 171–180. DOI: [10.5220/0009780501710180](https://doi.org/10.5220/0009780501710180).
- [2] T. Preisler, T. Dethlefs, and W. Renz, "Simulation as a service: A design approach for large-scale energy network simulations," *Proceedings of the 2015 Federated Conference on Computer Science and Information Systems, FedCSIS 2015*, vol. 5, pp. 1765–1772, 2015, ISBN: 9788360810651. DOI: [10.15439/2015F116](https://doi.org/10.15439/2015F116).

- [3] M. Gütlein and A. Djanatljev, “On-demand Simulation of Future Mobility Based on Apache Kafka,” *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol. 306, no. ViM, pp. 18–41, 2022, ISSN: 23673389. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-030-84811-8_2](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-84811-8_2).
- [4] M. Shahin, M. A. Babar, and M. A. Chauhan, “Architectural design space for modelling and simulation as a service: A review,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/2005.07883, 2020. arXiv: [2005.07883](https://arxiv.org/abs/2005.07883). [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2005.07883>.
- [5] L. Emele, M. Stappel, A. Kleinau, *et al.*, *Open Energy Ontology (OEO)*, version 2.6.0, Dec. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/ontology>.
- [6] M. Jensen, G. D. Colle, S. Kindya, C. More, A. P. Cox, and J. Beverley, *The common core ontologies*, 2024. arXiv: [2404.17758](https://arxiv.org/abs/2404.17758) [cs.AI]. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2404.17758>.
- [7] “SAREF extension for automotive.” (), [Online]. Available: <https://saref.etsi.org/saref4auto/v1.1.1/> (visited on 12/14/2024).
- [8] S. Bader, J. Pullmann, C. Mader, *et al.*, “The international data spaces information model – an ontology for sovereign exchange of digital content,” 2020, pp. 176–192. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-030-62466-8_12](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-62466-8_12).
- [9] J. S. Schwarz, C. Steinbrink, and S. Lehnhoff, “Towards an Assisted Simulation Planning for Co-Simulation of Cyber-Physical Energy Systems,” in *7th Workshop on Modeling and Simulation of Cyber-Physical Energy Systems (MSCPES)*, Montreal, 2019, pp. 1–6. DOI: [10.1109/MSCPES.2019.8738788](https://doi.org/10.1109/MSCPES.2019.8738788).
- [10] G. Dengler, P. Bazan, R. German, P. Lalbakhsh, and A. Liebmann, “A conversational human-computer interface for smart energy system simulation environments,” in *2023 Winter Simulation Conference (WSC)*, 2023, pp. 2978–2989. DOI: [10.1109/WSC60868.2023.10408707](https://doi.org/10.1109/WSC60868.2023.10408707).
- [11] T. Brown, J. Hörsch, and D. Schlachtberger, “PyPSA: Python for Power System Analysis,” *Journal of Open Research Software*, vol. 6, no. 4, 1 2018. DOI: [10.5334/jors.188](https://doi.org/10.5334/jors.188). eprint: [1707.09913](https://doi.org/10.5334/jors.188). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5334/jors.188>.
- [12] L. Thurner, A. Scheidler, F. Schäfer, *et al.*, “Pandapower — an open-source python tool for convenient modeling, analysis, and optimization of electric power systems,” *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 6510–6521, Nov. 2018, ISSN: 0885-8950. DOI: [10.1109/TPWRS.2018.2829021](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2018.2829021).
- [13] “OpenDSS.” (), [Online]. Available: <https://www.epri.com/pages/sa/opensdss> (visited on 12/14/2024).